

Reproducing Results from "Fast and Accurate User Cold-Start Learning Using Monte Carlo Tree Search"

AMÉLIE ASSMAYR, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

ANTONIO FURFARO SERRANÒ, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

ELINA MESSERITSCH, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

BARNABÁS PAKSI, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

MARTIN REICHHOLF, Vienna University of Technology, Austria

We attempt to reproduce the experimental setup, experiments, and results from the paper "Fast and Accurate User Cold-Start Learning Using Monte Carlo Tree Search" published by Douglas Leith and Dilina Chandika Rajapakse from Trinity College Dublin (2022). The information provided in the paper was not sufficient to fully reproduce all the results. For the results that we did manage to recreate, we could confirm the findings. No statistically significant differences were found between different settings.

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Recommender systems**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Experiment Design, Reproducibility, User cold start, Monte Carlo Tree Search, Decision Tree

1 Introduction

The paper "Fast and Accurate User Cold-Start Learning Using Monte Carlo Tree Search" [3] by Douglas Leith and Dilina Chandika Rajapakse from Trinity College Dublin proposes a Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS)-based method to efficiently solve the user cold-start problem. It claims to outperform decision tree (DT) and cluster-based bandit (CBB) approaches. This report attempts to recreate these findings and evaluates the reproducibility.

2 Experimental Setup and Strategy taken in the Paper

The paper builds on two previous papers [2], [5] of the supervisor, Douglas J. Leith, as well as the success of MCTS in two-player games and single-player games. BLC Matrix-factorization clustering is used on 3 commonly-used datasets with a good variability in the number of users and items as well. The algorithm is detailed in paper [2] but code was not available. Given the mean and standard deviation statistics from the clustered user groups, the CBB Algorithm [5] was first published against an optimized CART decision tree baseline with stellar performance in terms of accuracy. The current MCTS paper under review [3] is then built in the same setting, delivering even better accuracy. As for the speed differences, we gain no insight into the baseline models but results are shown for the MCTS approach. We note that existing datasets are a pre-requisite and the approach is aimed at companies with substantial existing datasets of user preferences.

3 Enablers and Obstacles in the Reproducibility Process

There were some positive aspects that helped us reproduce part of the results, but also some challenges that led to us not being able to reproduce everything.

On the positive side, a GitHub repository [4] of the authors was linked in the paper, containing part of the implementation code for the MCTS algorithm, item distribution data, which included the mean and variance of the clusters for each dataset, and some test data with 1000 users per

Authors' Contact Information: Amélie Assmayr, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria; Antonio Furfaro Serranò, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria; Elina Messeritsch, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria; Barnabás Paksi, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria; Martin Reichholf, Vienna University of Technology, Vienna, Austria.

group. Furthermore, there was a short explanation on how to run the code. We also found a short 11-minute video [3] in which one of the authors explained the algorithm.

The first challenge was that code for the baseline algorithms – the implementation of the decision tree and a cluster-based bandit algorithm – was not available online. Upon contacting the authors, we initially received a positive response but they never actually send the code or further instruction on the implementation. A paper on cluster-based bandits by the same supervisor [5] was referenced but the implementation was only given in pseudo-code and only for part of the algorithm. We were unable to implement it ourselves. Moreover, we suspect that the pseudo-code contained some errors which made the implementation hard. For the decision tree, we implemented a simple version on our own and tried a random forest for the smaller datasets to obtain more robust results. Another issue was that the uploaded code was not fully functional, and some adjustments were necessary to make it work, which will be discussed in more detail in section 4.

Secondly, running the code took a long time, especially for the larger datasets, highly exceeding time per recommendation claimed by the authors despite comparable hardware setups. While the authors used 8GB of RAM, for us, the MCTS with the netflix32 dataset required over 16GB.

The authors claim that sampling new user ratings from a normal distribution works just as well as using the original distributions. However, since they did not provide links to the original datasets or information on how to find them, we could not verify this claim. We found the original data for the Jester dataset; however, in the absence of the BLC matrix factorization algorithm [2], we did not attempt to reproduce the clustering.

Lastly, confirming the correctness of the distribution data without the original clusters was not possible. While the values for the Netflix dataset seemed plausible, for the Goodreads dataset all means were negative, even though ratings range from 0 to 5. This is exacerbated by the fact that the goodreads32 dataset contained only 24 groups, hinting at an oversight or omission by the authors. Similarly, while the Jester ratings have a range of -10 to 10, many means were lower than -10. Despite examples of such peculiarities, we believe this caused no major distortion to the results. The test data, which we assume was sampled from the distribution data, looked plausible again. For the test data we had the issue that the ground truth was not given. Since there were always $1000 * nr_groups$ users and files ended in `'_1000'` we assumed that the first 1000 users belonged to group1, the next 1000 to group2, etc.

4 Our Implementations

Our code, the data and all of our results can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/Amelie1313/Experiment-Design/tree/main>.

4.1 Implementation of Monte Carlo Decision Tree (MCTS)

The original paper contained a reference to a GitHub repository [1] containing their reference implementation. Using the provided code was not completely trivial as it did not compile out of the box. Further adjustment of the code was necessary as well in order to guarantee repeatable results. Some existing command line arguments were not implemented and had to be added, the code did not support seeding which had to be added, multi-threading had to be removed as it resulted in inconsistencies and the authors reported their results on a single CPU core as well. A CSV output that exports the whole resulting data was added, as the original program only reports statistics on this data.

Apart from that, the code implements the described algorithm in the paper correctly. It operates by taking mean and sigma files as inputs from which users are synthetically generated by a multinomial distribution. For these users, the MCTS algorithm is then applied as described in the original paper [3].

4.2 Implementation of Decision Tree (DT)

Since the original paper did not provide any implementation, we developed our own decision tree model. To achieve this, we utilized the datasets simulated by the authors. Initially, we introduced a variable indicating the group to which each user belongs. The dataset was then split into training and test sets, allocating 80% of the observations to the training set and 20% to the test set, ensuring stratification by groups.

During the training phase, we performed hyperparameter tuning to optimize the model's performance. Specifically, we fine-tuned the maximum tree depth (ranging from 3 to 30), the minimum number of observations per node (ranging from 1 to 50), and the complexity parameter (ranging from 0.0001 to 0.1), which determines whether a node split is worthwhile. Bayesian optimization was employed for this process, maximizing accuracy through 5-fold cross-validation.

After identifying the optimal hyperparameters, we trained the decision tree on the entire training set and subsequently evaluated its performance on the test set. This procedure was repeated for each dataset while incrementally introducing a new variable related to the rating of an additional item, continuing until a total of 25 items had been rated.

4.3 Implementation of Cluster based bandits (CBB)

Although the cluster-based bandit algorithm was not directly provided in the paper [5], we attempted to implement it, as it was the stronger baseline of the two displayed in the results. Unfortunately, we noticed inconsistencies in the pseudo-code which we could not correct based on the descriptions alone. In particular, on page 1614, the $R_n(g, h)$ function definition is not in line with references to it over the paper. Algorithm 2, line 2 also appears to contain an error, as an unrated item's rating (v_n) is used for a calculation. Due to these major discrepancies and insufficient detail in the descriptions, we abandoned our efforts trying to re-implement the cluster-based bandits algorithm.

5 Results

Overall, we were able to reproduce most of the results from the authors. Since we were not able to implement the CBB algorithm, we focused on the decision tree and MCTS for our comparison.

Results in the original paper were reported for 1000 synthetic users per group (t); however, running the code with 1000 users per group took an excessively long time. Accordingly, we tried reducing the number to 100 and 15, performing statistical tests to confirm that reducing the sample size does not radically alter the results. We only did this comparison for three of the 16 datasets, since the computation time for all 6 datasets with 1000 users would have taken too long. For example, the computation for the netflix4 dataset took approximately 18 hours and the jester8 dataset took approximately 37 hours, so trying out all datasets would not have been feasible. Table 1 shows that different numbers of users per group led to extremely similar results. To make sure that the differences were not statistically significant, we performed a Friedman test. We chose a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$, which will also be used for all the following tests. The result was a p-value of 0.3679, indicating that there is no significant difference between the results when using different numbers of users per group. Therefore, we reduced t to 100 instead of 1000 for all datasets with the exception of netflix32, where we had to use $t=15$, because otherwise we ran out of memory.

Given the result of the Friedman test, we began recreating the key tables and visuals using the reduced sample size. Table 2 compares our results to those from the authors for the decision tree (DT) and the Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) for the Netflix dataset. The results for MCTS are very similar across all numbers of groups. For the decision tree, our implementation performed better for datasets with fewer groups but worse for datasets with more groups. Overall, we could confirm the findings for the Netflix dataset that Monte Carlo Tree Search outperforms the optimized

decision tree and the CBB methods based on the performance reported by the authors as well as our implementation for the decision tree.

While the MCTS promises higher accuracy, it is time consuming. We compare the mean MCTS computation time to recommend the next item to a new user reported in [3] to our measurements. We obtained significantly slower recommendations with an AMD Ryzen 7 5700X 8-Core, 3401Mhz processor and 64GB of 2400 Mhz RAM. To see if investing time in improving the accuracy is really worth it, we performed a one-sided Wilcoxon-test to determine if the MCTS yields significantly higher performance. Obtaining a p-value of 0.00024, allowed us to reject the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference between the results, i.e. the MCTS is better.

Table 1. Performance Evaluation for Monte Carlo Tree Search

Dataset	# users per group		
	15	100	1000
Netflix 4	1.000	0.997	1.000
Jester 4	0.950	0.940	0.948
Jester 8	0.867	0.881	0.890

(a) Accuracy for different number of users per groups

Dataset	#groups	average time	
		Rajapakse	Assmayr
Netflix	16	86.10ms	323.20ms
Goodreads	16	46.78ms	194.40ms
Jester	16	19.17ms	93.20ms

(b) Mean MCTS computation time to recommend next item to a new user

We could also confirm the results for the other two rating platforms which can be seen in Figure 1.

(a) Accuracy of Jester dataset

(b) Accuracy of Goodreads dataset

Fig. 1. Accuracy vs. number of iteration: Comparison of implementations

Figure 2 shows the probability-evolution vs. number of items for group 4 for the netflix8 dataset. Again, we could confirm the findings of the authors. For us, group 4 was the group with the highest probability from the beginning, but, just like in the original paper, all the other probabilities quickly became smaller while the probability for group 4 increased quickly soon.

Table 2. Comparison of DT and MCTS algorithms across different group sizes and iterations.
 *The Netflix 32 dataset was only tested with 15 users per group due to computational constraints.

# Groups	Algorithm	Implementation	# Iterations				
			5	10	15	20	25
4	DT	Ours	0.729	0.842	0.860	0.889	0.892
		Authors	0.672	0.795	0.795	0.795	0.795
	MCTS	Ours	0.942	0.988	0.990	0.998	1.000
		Authors	0.951	0.988	0.997	0.999	1.000
8	DT	Ours	0.542	0.666	0.736	0.749	0.760
		Authors	0.674	0.780	0.780	0.780	0.780
	MCTS	Ours	0.805	0.959	0.982	0.995	0.995
		Authors	0.838	0.962	0.987	0.994	0.997
16	DT	Ours	0.307	0.463	0.522	0.548	0.581
		Authors	0.566	0.628	0.631	0.631	0.631
	MCTS	Ours	0.586	0.846	0.912	0.947	0.968
		Authors	0.649	0.853	0.920	0.949	0.965
32*	DT	Ours	0.223	0.321	0.351	0.375	0.375
		Authors	0.327	0.414	0.425	0.423	0.423
	MCTS	Ours	0.379	0.608	0.748	0.771	0.842
		Authors	0.437	0.642	0.739	0.797	0.836

(a) Our Implementation

(b) Authors Implementation

Fig. 2. Probability-evaluation vs. number of items for group 4

In order to test whether the results would hold if the experiment was repeated multiple times, we tried eight different seeds. As can be seen in Table 3 the results are extremely similar for all seeds. The standard deviation for the accuracies of each dataset ranged between 0.0008 for Netflix 4 and 0.0156 for Jester 4. To be sure that the results were also statistically indistinguishable, we performed a Friedman test and obtained a p-value of 0.092 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, we cannot reject the null hypothesis which states that there is no statistically significant difference.

We calculated the means and confidence intervals across results obtained with varying seeds, over 8 observations. Bootstrapping was used to calculate the intervals due to the low number of observations. The results can be found in Table 4. Even if we happened to select a seed with

the performance in the Lower Bound column, accuracy results would be superior to the reported baselines in all cases.

Table 3. MCTS Accuracy for different seeds

Dataset	Seeds							
	88666223	73308559	63381133	61451749	45755797	93643757	83638859	34521869
Goodreads 4	0.990	0.995	0.997	0.995	0.992	1.000	0.995	0.995
Goodreads 8	0.927	0.934	0.920	0.920	0.925	0.926	0.938	0.912
Jester 4	0.940	0.952	0.960	0.930	0.940	0.947	0.980	0.970
Jester 8	0.890	0.901	0.874	0.887	0.881	0.883	0.890	0.874
Netflix 4	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.997	1.000	1.000	1.000
Netflix 8	0.992	0.991	0.997	0.994	0.992	0.999	0.999	0.995

Table 4. Mean accuracy and confidence intervals for different datasets.

Dataset	Mean	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Goodreads 4	0.995	0.993	0.997
Goodreads 8	0.925	0.92	0.931
Jester 4	0.952	0.942	0.964
Jester 8	0.884	0.879	0.888
Netflix 4	1.000	0.999	1.000
Netflix 8	0.995	0.993	0.997

6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the paper is partially reproducible. Missing code for baselines prevents one from recreating some results, since it is not clear how the missing code can be implemented. However, for the results that we could reproduce, we could confirm the findings in multiple different settings. We can confirm that the Monte Carlo Tree Search is an accurate method for user cold-start problems. However we would challenge the claim that it is a fast method as the authors claimed in their title since it took a significantly longer than the decision tree algorithms. Overall, the authors are on the right way to ensure reproducibility with just a few shortcomings that could easily be fixed.

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